

ISSN 2181-9599

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9599

ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

5 ЖИЛД, 10 СОН

ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 10

LOOK TO THE PAST

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 10

ТОШКЕНТ-2022

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**THE NEW UZBEKISTAN IS A COUNTRY OF GREAT POTENTIAL
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF WOMEN)**

For citation: Rakhbar E.Kholikova. THE NEW UZBEKISTAN IS A COUNTRY OF GREAT POTENTIAL (ON THE EXAMPLE OF WOMEN). Look to the past. 2022, vol. 5, issue 10, pp.4-8

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7329060>

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the fact that women work effectively in all spheres of society, fully demonstrate their talents and potential, and play an important role in socio-economic and spiritual reforms. Raising the status and place of women in society is one of the most important priorities of our state policy. The practical evidence of the attention paid to women is the recent adoption of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at strengthening the role and influence of women in society. Socio-legal support for women, professional, physical, spiritual and intellectual development, increasing their socio-political activity and creating all opportunities for women to show their potential are the criteria of our development. In order to protect women from various levels of financial hardship, a number of systemic measures are being taken in our country. The article provides a detailed analysis of the adoption of the "Program to Support Women's Education" for 2022-2026 and the work being done in this direction.

Index Terms: women, national institutions, grant, higher education, credit, subsidy, entrepreneurship, committee, "Ayollar daftari", medical, legal, psychological assistance.

1.Relevance:

One of the commendable aspects of our state policy is that the reforms being carried out in our country are aimed at the interests of women. In particular, as noted by the President, "Ensuring the legitimate rights and interests of women, increasing their economic, social and political activity has become one of the important directions of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan to achieve the highest goal - to please our people" [From the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the International Women's Day]. If we pay attention to the essence of these words of our President, we will see that the ongoing reforms make a significant contribution to improving the quality of life of women, helping them to find their place in society, to significantly improve their quality of life.

2. Methods:

The article is based on the principles of nationally accepted historical methods - historical, comparative and logical analysis, consistency, objectivity.

3. Research results:

We know that in recent years, the issue of comprehensive support for women in our country, strengthening their status has become one of the priorities of public policy. We see this in the example of many practical efforts and real results. possible. The level of socio-political activity of women in society is one of the important criteria in assessing the development of our country. The socio-political status of women in Uzbekistan is growing, and they are making a significant contribution to large-scale reforms in all spheres of life. After gaining independence, the organizational and legal framework for women's participation in all spheres of state and public administration was created. It should be noted that the participation of women in the economic, socio-political life of the country is growing day by day.

To date, national mechanisms have been established to promote and develop women's rights, as well as national institutions to strengthen their role in all spheres of political, economic and social life. This can be seen in the fact that women's participation in political parties has increased from 36% to 50%.

Currently, 32% of deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, members of the Senate and the Jogorku Kenesh of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, about 25% of deputies of local councils of people's deputies are women. This has reached the level set by the UN recommendations. The country's parliament has risen to 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of women.

Today, more than 50% of workers and employees in various sectors of the country are women. In particular, about 1,400 women hold leadership positions at the national and regional levels, and more than 43,000 at district and city levels.

Of course, behind these numbers lies the process of hard work, responsibility for their work, constant research, continuous improvement of skills and abilities.

Entrepreneurship is a type of work that is done according to the free time and desires of women. It not only brings extra income to women, but also allows them to realize their social qualities and abilities.

In 2021, 2 trillion soums of loans and subsidies were allocated for more than 200,000 projects under the Women's Entrepreneurship Program, and 320,000 women had permanent jobs. 190,000 women were trained. More than 4,000 women were allocated the initial cost of housing.

In total, starting in 2020, the Women's Notebook system will be launched, providing socio-economic, medical, legal and psychological assistance to about 900,000 women included in it.

"Women depend on us for a prosperous life today and a bright future. If we want our people to be happy with us, we must first create decent living conditions for our mothers and sisters. If the mother agrees, the family agrees, if the family agrees, the society agrees, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

This goal is one of the most important directions in the development strategy of our country. The Presidential Decree on the establishment of the State Committee for Family and Women's Affairs was adopted to ensure their systematic implementation in each neighborhood. The committee is now managed by the State Targeted Fund for Women's Support and the "Ayollar daftari".

Woman is the future of the nation, the successor of life. The present and the future of the country, where women are respected and valued, will be peaceful and prosperous, and with the labor of women, society will fully develop and prosper. That is why in our country special attention is paid to women and more and more attention is paid to relieving their burden.

In the era of New Uzbekistan, a period of great social and political changes, new challenges are being identified that define the role of women in the modern world, and by addressing them, a new stage of development can be achieved.

Based on the noble principle that **“no one is left out of love and attention,”** in 2021, nearly 900,000 women received socio-economic, medical, legal and psychological assistance. 2 trillion soums were allocated from the budget for these purposes. In particular, 18 billion women received soft loans worth 400 billion soums to buy a house. A budget was introduced to cover the expenses of kindergartens for the children of women who had lost their breadwinners.

In our country, the number of jobs created on the basis of programs aimed at ensuring women's employment, which are relevant today, is growing every year. Achievements in supporting women's entrepreneurship are commendable. Particularly noteworthy are efforts to promote domestic labor. This, in turn, allows women to make a worthy contribution to the family's financial well-being, as well as to be directly involved in child rearing.

Significant work is being done in our country to strengthen the community and family institutions, which are the main link in society.

The great enlightener Abdullah Avloni said, **"Girls should strive for education more than anyone else, because with this knowledge they will educate the next generation."**

Since the goal of our progress is to achieve the Third Renaissance, our main task should be to make our women more educated, more enlightened in this direction.

It should be noted that **an enlightened woman** is the path of development of society, because it is she who educates children and shapes their consciousness, worldview, level of knowledge.

However, the more educated a girl is, the more knowledgeable and talented she will be, the more she will pass it on to her children in the future, and the more she will take a responsible approach to raising a harmoniously developed generation. Because by nature and nature, women have a great responsibility to continue the chain of generations and to raise children who will uphold the dignity of the nation.

A woman's interest in science and intelligence is the basis for her family and children to be cultured. Our state pays great attention to the education of our women and girls. In particular, in 2021, more than 2,000 girls from needy families were admitted to universities on the basis of state grants, and the same number of students were paid contract fees.

In her speeches, the President said: "Because of our special focus on women's education, 60 percent of the students admitted to universities last year were women.

If six years ago, 110,000 of our girls were educated in universities, today their number has reached 400,000, or their share has risen from 38% in 2016 to almost 50% today. "

It is well known that in any country, the level of maturity of the people is determined, first of all, by the scientific and cultural maturity of women, and intelligent and educated mothers create the great future of the nation. In his congratulatory message on the occasion of International Women's Day, the President said:

It is no coincidence that he emphasized the wise saying, **"If you teach one girl, you will teach the whole family."**

"We will continue to work to ensure that our girls have modern knowledge and skills and find a worthy place in society and in their families. In this regard, we will first adopt **the National Program to Support Women's Education** for 2022-2026. As part of this document, we will organize a separate university for women in the capital and its technical schools in the field. An interest-free loan for 7 years will be introduced for all female students to pay for their education contracts.

As a logical continuation of this work, we will take to a new level the work of supporting women scientists who are making a significant contribution to the development of our country through their scientific research and discoveries."

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further accelerate the work on systematic support of families and women" provides for the comprehensive development of the education system in Uzbekistan and the expansion of women's participation in it. It is no coincidence that important new initiatives and ideas have been put forward to ensure the social protection of workers in the sector.

Looking back, it is worth noting that the role of scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of science, enlightenment and spirituality of our country is invaluable.

In our society, women's mastery of the secrets of science, the use of their abilities and potential for the development of society is a guarantee of social activism for the future of New Uzbekistan.

“Today, there are dozens of academics and professors, doctors and candidates of science, and hundreds of talented researchers among our sisters. Doing science and innovating is like digging a well with a needle.”

“We have identified a number of important measures to increase the interest and enthusiasm of intelligent and knowledgeable women in science. In particular, starting from the next academic year, 200 billion soums will be allocated annually to fully cover the contract money of all girls studying for a master's degree from the budget; There will be at least 300 targeted quotas for doctoral students each year.”

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 of March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate the work on systemic support of families and women" - The task is to allocate at least 300 targeted quotas for girls each year.

In order to systematically organize and coordinate this work, the Society of Women Scholars will be established under the State Committee for Family and Women. This society will unite our women scientists, who are making great strides in the field of science in our country and abroad, and will become a unique platform for their intellectual light to penetrate into every aspect of our lives.”

As long as our scientists in the new Uzbekistan are active in such a society, they will not only contribute to the development of science through the world information system, but also get acquainted with its innovations, share their talents and achievements in science at home and abroad. have the right to demonstrate.

In order to properly encourage the hard and honorable work of hard-working scientists, to create favorable conditions for them in all respects, the Society of Women Scientists is allocated 50 billion soums annually.

In general, 1.8 trillion soums will be allocated for all the above goals for the current and next year. ”

Of course, it is important to systematically organize and coordinate support for women. In accordance with Decree PF-87, the post of Deputy Prime Minister was re-established and the State Committee on Family and Women was established to ensure the implementation of priorities in this regard. The heads of the provincial, district and city administrations of the committee were given the status of deputy governors.

The posts of women and family deputy chairmen of about 9,500 mahallas in the country have also been transferred to the committee system, and the positions of women activists have been re-introduced in each mahalla. It was all the right thing to do, the right decision. This is because a new way of working, which extends to the lowest levels of the community and the home, will help to effectively implement public policy in this regard.

In this way, a fair and effective system has been created that constantly deals with the problems and concerns of our sisters.

Conclusion:

An important aspect of the state policy is that in recent years, women in Uzbekistan are given a high level of care, and many problems that have plagued them for years are being solved and eliminated one after another.

The responsibilities and obligations of parents, the public, bureaucrats have been increased to protect the health of our women, to ensure that they have a modern profession, are educated and have a place in society.

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Tadqiqot.uz

ISSN 2181-9599

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9599

ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

5 ЖИЛД, 18 СОН

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ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 18

LOOK TO THE PAST

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 18

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

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